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ENLIGHT RISE- RESEARCH AND INNOVATION AGENDA WITH AND FOR SOCIETY: LEVERAGING DIGITAL INNOVATION FOR A GREENER AND HEALTHIER EUROPE

WP No	Del. Rel. No	Del No	Title	Lead beneficiary
1	D1.5	D5	Action and development plan for matching tool	UT

Nature	Dissemination Level	Related to Del. No (if applicable)
Report	Public	

Description (short)
This document summarises a survey conducted to get an understanding of what matching tools and methods are in place within ENLIGHT. It also provides a summary of the needs that partners would like to see met with help of the digital matching tool. The report then presents two options for what form the digital matching tool could take, taking into account other ENLIGHT RISE developments since the beginning of the project.

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Abbreviations

ENLIGHT partner	Short Name	Country
University of Bordeaux	UBx	FR
Ghent University	UGent	BE
Comenius University Bratislava	CU	SK
University of the Basque Country	UPV/EHU	ES
University of Galway	Gal	IE
University of Göttingen	UGOE	DE
University of Groningen	RUG	NL
University of Tartu	UT	EE
Uppsala University	UU	SE

Introduction

ENLIGHT is a European University formed by nine comprehensive research-intensive universities from nine European countries (University of the Basque Country in Spain, University of Bordeaux in France, Comenius University Bratislava in Slovakia, University of Galway in Ireland, Ghent University in Belgium, University of Göttingen in Germany, University of Groningen in the Netherlands, University of Tartu in Estonia, Uppsala University in Sweden).

ENLIGHT has obtained funding from the European Commission in the framework of the Horizon 2020 Science With and For Society (SwafS) work programme. The ENLIGHT RISE project (Research and Innovation agenda with and for Society) seeks to strengthen the research and innovation dimension of the ENLIGHT alliance.

To develop a harmonized approach for researcher/funding matching within ENLIGHT and promote cooperation between its researchers, the alliance will develop a digital matching tool. This tool will provide researchers from the ENLIGHT alliance with valuable information about potential funding opportunities for their research while also providing information about potential collaborators within the alliance.

To find a common ground for the development of the ENLIGHT matching tool, we started with a survey on the current approaches towards researcher/funding matching among the 9 partners. Furthermore, we collected the expectations of the partners regarding the ENLIGHT digital matching tool. At the same time, we reflected on the developments within ENLIGHT RISE that have taken place so far, such as the creation of the ENLIGHT Research and Innovation Observatory. This document lays the groundwork for developing the ENLIGHT digital matching tool by presenting the results of this work, and proposes two options for developing the network-wide matching tool. These options will be further explored together with all consortium partners to select the most cost-effective and beneficial solution. The more detailed technical plan for the tool will be presented in D1.7 Development plan digital matching tool (M25). D1.7 will describe the timetable for development, testing and pilot implementation, the application programming interface, the underlying languages, etc.

Methodology: partner survey on existing (digital) matching tools

To create an overview illustrating the present status of researcher/funding matching within the ENLIGHT Alliance, a survey among the 9 partners was conducted, from 3.10.2022 to 14.10.2022.

The survey was implemented in the LimeSurvey platform. It was distributed among the ENLIGHT partner university WP1 members with the goal of having one result from every partner. The intention was to reach out to a limited group of support office staff who would have a good understanding of the situation at their university. The survey consisted of the following 10 questions:

1. Which partner university are you from?
2. Who is submitting this response (Name and email)?
3. What online solutions or databases are in use at your university regarding finding funding opportunities for researchers?
4. Besides the online solutions and/or databases, how is the matching of funding opportunities with researchers/institutions managed?
5. What online solutions or databases are in use at your university regards finding potential collaboration partners for researchers?
6. Besides the online solutions and/or databases, how is the finding of potential collaboration partners for researchers/institutions managed?
7. Does your institution use any publicly available log in methods (ORCID etc.)?
8. In your experience, what are the biggest issues regarding how researchers find suitable funding opportunities and partners for a research project?
9. What would you expect from a digital matching tool for managing funding opportunities and partner searches for researchers within the ENLIGHT network?
10. Are you aware of any good digital matching solutions used by other universities/networks/alliances? If yes, please provide a short description and/or a link to the information.

Results of the partner survey

The survey resulted in 10 answers from 9 different ENLIGHT alliance members – one member provided two answers (both were used in the analysis for completeness).

The results were as follows:

Question 3 - What online solutions or databases are in use at your university regarding finding funding opportunities for researchers?

The most common database used was Research Professional (used by 3 partner universities) followed by CrowdHelix (1 university), Open4research (1 university) and Funding Institutional (1 university). As seen in the results, while Research Professional was used in 3 institutions, there is no ubiquitous database or solution used by all partners. The only common database used by all partner institutions, is the European Commission's Funding & Tenders Portal.

Question 4 - Besides the online solutions and/or databases, how is the matching of funding opportunities with researchers/institutions managed?

These solutions were mainly case by case matching of funding opportunities to researchers or the other way by support staff. These also included internal meetings and other internal ways of communications, like e-mail list etc organized by support staff.

Question 5 - What online solutions or databases are in use at your university regards finding potential collaboration partners for researchers?

The most common databases used in this regard were CrowdHelix (used by 3 partner universities), SciVal (1 university) and CORDIS (1 university). As with question 3, there is no database or solution that is in use in the majority of the institutions.

Question 6 - Besides the online solutions and/or databases, how is the finding of potential collaboration partners for researchers/institutions managed?

These answers were similar to what was answered to question 4 – manual, internal communication tools that mostly rely on some source of bibliographical data or project information managed by support staff. For example, internal partner databases based on past experiences, matchmakings, but also actions like COST and ENLIGHT partner search.

Question 7 - Does your institution use any publicly available log in methods (ORCID etc.)?

While most of the institutions use ORCID and/or other methods (ResearcherID) in some form, by encouraging researchers to create profiles for example, there are no financially optimal, user-friendly and publicly available methods to get all the researchers from the 9 partner institutions into one place. ORCID credentials for

example would have provided a secure method for this, but it is not possible to limit the log-in to ENLIGHT partners only.

Question 8 - In your experience, what are the biggest issues regarding how researchers find suitable funding opportunities and partners for a research project?

The issues regarding the matching are quite similar among the alliance partners. When it comes to matching funding opportunities to researchers, there are periods of time when there are too many opportunities for researchers and/or support staff to work through, while during other periods there are no opportunities available. Issues also arise with cross-cluster calls. Depending on the researchers' domain of expertise, they often identify themselves with calls in one particular cluster, while due to the interdisciplinary nature of the calls, opportunities also exist in other clusters that they might not be aware of or don't follow-up on.

Question 9 - What would you expect from a digital matching tool for managing funding opportunities and partner searches for researchers within the ENLIGHT network?

The expectations vary from very high and specific, to minimal, with some of the expectations not aligned with what is optimal and financially plausible. Examples of the answers include:

- We are happy with the tools we already have, such as Research Professionals. We don't believe in a tool for partner searches for researchers.
- It would be extremely useful if the tool could alert researchers on who can be ideal partners for them and their consortium (based on expertise and requirements of the call):
 1. The call is brought to the researcher's attention
 2. The tool shows you the right partner for your proposal
- To establish a network of contacts in strategic areas between the 9 universities participating in the project that can serve as a starting point for the creation of new research consortia in the framework of the Horizon Europe programme as well as other international programmes (without prejudice to the possibility of partners from other universities joining).

Question 10 - Are you aware of any good digital matching solutions used by other universities/networks/alliances? If yes, please provide a short description and/or a link to the information.

Partners listed a few good examples of how different institutions have managed digital solutions. These were both internal tools developed by the institutions and commercial tools provided by different companies, for example Dimensions (dimensions.ai), CrowdHelix (crowdhelix.com), Impacter (impacter.eu) and MyEUFunding Apps from the University of Southern Denmark.

Plans for the ENLIGHT digital matching tool

For the matching tool there is a need for two types of information. Firstly, there is a need for information about funding opportunities – the deadline, topic (area) etc. This information can be accessed through a database or be entered by administrators. The other form of information needed is the information about the researchers at the partner universities. This information should include information about the research areas where the individual is working and if possible basic information about the career stage. This information should be provided by the researcher or come from a general (researcher) database. The idea behind the digital tool is to combine these two types of information to provide researchers with, on the one hand, information about funding opportunities that match their interests and field and, on the other hand, with information about potential partners from within ENLIGHT suitable for these funding opportunities.

As seen from the results of the survey, there is no one commercial solution used by all partners that would allow us to combine all the necessary aspects of the matching from funding opportunities to user management. The only aspect that can be covered, is the source of funding opportunities. Since all the partner universities are familiar with the European Commission's Funding & Tenders Portal and it holds the most valuable information regarding the European Union funding opportunities, it is only right that we continue to use it. This option is also financially beneficial as this source of information is free. But when it comes to information about the researchers (more than 30 000) in all 9 institutions, there is no existing database that could cover this in an easy and practical way.

Therefore, we have identified the following primary options to move forward:

1. Build a fully separate ENLIGHT database that combines the information from the Funding & Tenders Portal with information about the researchers. While this option would allow for targeted researcher/researcher matching, it would be rather costly since it needs the resources and time to develop a separate

database. In particular, it would be challenging to collect all the needed information about more than 30 000 researchers in the ENLIGHT Alliance manually and to keep it continuously up-to-date. At the same time, as explained above, ORCID cannot be used for this as it will not be possible to limit access to researchers from partner institutions only. Additional resources for building such a database for the alliance could come for example from European Excellence Initiative, but securing this funding will take time.

2. Use information available in the [ENLIGHT R&I Observatory](#). The observatory already has a substantial overview of the research groups/labs operating in the alliance. This means that only information about the funding opportunities needs to be added and the matching could be done in the observatory. This could be the most feasible option within the project duration, which will address the concerns related to creation of new user names/passwords by researchers and will not create massive amount of extra work for support staff.

In the next step of the process, we will further explore the above two options in terms of feasibility, cost-effectiveness and sustainability, together with all ENLIGHT partners. This will include the following actions:

- Each institution will need to consider their ability to collect information about their researchers for the ENLIGHT database, as well as a longer-term ability to keep it up-to-date
- UT in cooperation with UBx will explore how the ENLIGHT R&I Observatory could be exploited – by using the data available in it or integrating the digital matching tool as part of it

Based on the above steps, UT will prepare D1.7 describing the timetable for development, testing and pilot implementation of the tool, the application programming interface, the underlying languages, etc. D1.7 will be completed by M25.

Appendix 1 - ENLIGHT RISE Survey for Digital Matching Tool

Task: Develop an action plan for grant/researcher and researcher/researcher matching in ENLIGHT (M6-M18)

Based on their current procedures and goals for increased researcher/funding matching, ENLIGHT partners will create a strategy for network-wide matching of researchers and funding. We will analyze approaches used outside of our network, conduct alignment between partners, who have different approaches, systems, and resources. Once common ground has been established, we will specify actions to implement the strategy. This includes actions to fill gaps to enable increased collaboration (e.g., partners who lack databases of their researchers will develop them during this project): we will identify national/international funding opportunities to support this implementation.

The aim of the survey is to understand what approaches towards researcher/funding matching are used by 9 partner universities so we can find common ground for the development of the digital matching tool for the ENLIGHT network. There is no need to go into a very detailed description of solutions and databases here, but if further information is needed we will get in touch.

Information from the survey will be made available to other partners and it will be part of the public deliverable. If some of the information is regarded as confidential by the institution please add "Confidential" in parentheses, and we will not include it in the deliverable.

Only one answer from each partner is required. Further information and questions can be addressed to Kalmer Lauk at University of Tartu (kalmer.lauk@ut.ee)

Which partner university are you from? *
Please write your answer here:

Who is submitting this response (Name and email)? *
Please write your answer here:

What online solutions or databases are in use at your university regarding finding funding opportunities for researchers?

Please write your answer here:

Besides the online solutions and/or databases, how is the matching of funding opportunities with researchers/institutions managed?

Please write your answer here:

What online solutions or databases are in use at your university regards finding potential collaboration partners for researchers?

Please write your answer here:

Besides the online solutions and/or databases, how is the finding of potential collaboration partners for researchers/institutions managed?

Please write your answer here:

Does your institution use any publicly available log in methods (ORCID etc.)?

Please write your answer here:

In your experience, what are the biggest issues regarding how researchers find suitable funding opportunities and partners for research project?

Please write your answer here:

What would you expect from a digital matching tool for managing funding opportunities and partner searches for researchers within the ENLIGHT network?

Please write your answer here:

Are you aware of any good digital matching solutions used by other universities/networks/alliances? If yes, please provide a short description and/or a link to the information.

Please write your answer here:

Submit your survey.

Thank you for completing this survey.